

Bash scripts for long-read sequencing data analysis

For each sample (uMRT Rep1/Rep2 and Maxima Rep1/Rep2):

1. Trim sequencing adaptors with Porechop

```
porechop -i /path/to/fastq.gz \  
-o /path/to/output_folder/trimmed_fastq.gz --discard_middle
```

2. Trim TSO sequences (after adding the TSO sequences manually in the adapters.py file)

```
porechop -i /path/to/fastq.gz \  
-o /path/to/output_folder/barcode_and_TSO_trimmed_fastq.gz --discard_middle
```

3. Mapping with Minimap2

```
minimap2 -ax map-ont /path/to/reference_fasta/reference.fna  
/path/to/barcode_and_TSO_trimmed_fastq.gz > /path/to/output_folder/aligned.sam
```

4. Converting SAM to BAM and sorting BAM

```
samtools view -b -T /path/to/reference/fasta.fa /path/to/aligned.sam >  
path/to/output_folder/aligned.bam
```

```
samtools sort aligned.bam > aligned_sorted.bam
```

5. Quantification with IsoQuant

```
path/to/isoquant.py --reference /path/to/reference_Fasta/reference.fna  
--genedb /path/to/reference_GTF/reference.gtf  
--bam path/to/aligned.bam \  
--data_type nanopore \  
-o /path/to/output_folder/
```

6. FASTA conversion with seqtk

```
seqtk seq -a path/to/reads.fastq.gz > path/to/output_folder/reads.fasta
```

7. Sequence length determination with samtools

```
samtools faidx reads.fasta
```

Code for downsampling:

```
seqtk sample /path/to/reads.fastq.gz 1200000 > subsampled_reads.fastq.gz
```